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The development and loss of directional deixis in the history of English

Riassunto: Proprio come la maggior parte delle lingue romanze, l'inglese ha quasi completamente perso i mezzi formali per distinguere tra *posizione* e *direzione* nel corso della sua storia. Partendo dalle distinzioni fatte nell'inglese antico tra i due concetti nella sua grammatica e lessico, questo articolo analizza i corrispondenti sistemi di dimostrativi, avverbi e forme pronominali interrogative per i diversi periodi storici dell'inglese, con un focus sui sottosistemi spaziali, inclusi i loro aspetti formali e semantici (uso spaziale *vs.* esteso), il loro sviluppo storico e la loro perdita. I risultati di questo studio descrittivo sono riassunti e discussi da una prospettiva più generale, comparativa e tipologica, rivelando così proprietà caratteristiche dell'inglese contemporaneo.

Parole Chiave: dimostrativi, direzionalità, cambiamento semantico, asimmetrie, valutazione comparativa

Abstract: Just like most Romance languages, English has almost completely lost the formal means of distinguishing between LOCATION and DIRECTION in the course of its history. Starting out from the distinctions made in OE between the two concepts in its grammar and lexicon, this paper analyses the relevant systems of demonstratives, adverbs and interrogative pro-forms for the different historical periods of English, with a focus on the spatial subsystems, including their formal and semantic properties (spatial *vs.* extended use), their historical development and their loss. The results of this descriptive survey are summarized and discussed from a more general, comparative and typological perspective, thus revealing characteristic properties of Pres.-Day English.

Keywords: demonstratives, directionality, semantic change, asymmetries, comparative evaluation

1. Introduction

The structuring and encoding of space through language, the shape of the linguistic inventories found in individual languages and across languages, as well as the symmetries and asymmetries manifested by such systems have received a great deal of attention during the last four decades (e.g. Talmy 1985; Ikegami 1987; Stefanowitch – Rohde 2004; Pantcheva 2010; Bohnemeyer – Enfield – Essegbey – Ibarretxe-Antuñano – Kita – Lüpke – Amerka, 2007; Kopecka – Vuillemet 2021, etc.). The vast majority of the relevant studies adopted a purely

synchronic perspectives and diachronic studies of the relevant phenomena, such as Luraghi – Nikitina – Zanchi (2017), Huber (2017) and Stefanowitsch (2018) are rare exceptions. Taking up some of the issues discussed in these volumes, our paper aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the developments in the encoding of space in English by means of spatial demonstratives and spatial adverbs.

Just like most Romance languages (cf. Stolz – Levkovych – Urdze 2017), Present Day English (henceforth PDE) has almost completely lost the formal means of distinguishing between location and direction in the course of its history. In addition to the loss of case distinctions (*in* + dative *vs.* *in* + accusative, cf. (1)), to reductions in the system of prepositional oppositions (*onto* > *on*, cf. (2)) and to the loss of distinctions in subsystems of adverbs (OE. *ūtan* – *ūte* – *ūt* *vs.* PDE (*from* *outside*)), it was especially the loss of directional deictic expressions and directional interrogatives which led to this fundamental change. The distinctions expressed in more conservative Germanic languages, like Icelandic and German, by special locational (“inessive”) or directional (“ablative” and “allative”) markers are now mainly carried by stative *vs.* dynamic verbs (cf. (3) – (5)):

- (1) a. uton nu geþencan, broðor mine, hwylc ure eard is in þissum middanearde
1PL. IMP now think, brother my which our home is in this: DAT world: DAT
(HomS (Willard) 31 1)¹.
[Let us think, my brother, which is our home in this world]
- b. ða astag he in scip, & com in Fresena land
then got he in ship[ACC] and came in Frisian: GEN; PL land[ACC]
(Bede 5 9.412.19 cf. Bede. Hist. eccl. 5.9, 478 Fresiam perueniens).
[then he got on the ship and came to Friesland]
- (2) He jumped onto the table. – He jumped on the table.
- (3) a. John is outside/upstairs/next door.
b. John went outside/upstairs/next door.
- (4) a. John emigrated to Canada and he still lives there.
b. I would love to go there, too.
- (5) a. John is sitting on the bench. – John sat (down) on the bench.
b. The milk is in the fridge. – I put the milk in the fridge.

Old English, by contrast, still manifests a clear distinction between LOCATION and DIRECTION in its case system, its systems of adverbial forms and prepositions, as well as in its systems of demonstratives and interrogatives, just like

¹ All the data for OE are taken from the *DOE* Web Corpus and quoted according to the *DOE* A-I online.

Old Icelandic, Modern Icelandic and Old High German. Moreover, like the early stages of the other Germanic languages, OE not only distinguishes location from direction, but also differentiates within the category DIRECTION between (movement to a) GOAL (*hider* ‘hither’ – *þider* ‘thither’) and (movement away from a) SOURCE (*heonon* ‘from here’ – *þanon* ‘from there’), opposing a proximal to a distal exponent in each case. The focus of our paper is on the historical development of spatial demonstratives and adverbs in English, considered in the more comprehensive context of the reduction of deictic distinctions, of distinctions between location and direction and of the survival of non-spatial meanings in the demonstratives of PDE.

Demonstratives are referential expressions, pro-forms rather than fully specified phrases, which identify a referent in terms of its distance from a center of orientation, typically the coordinates of the speech situation. They are deictic expressions and can thus be accompanied by pointing, enacting or mimicking gestures, thus establishing and coordinating a joint center of interest (Diessel 1999, 2006). Being PRO-forms, demonstratives have a relatively simple semantic structure, typically expressing a deictic component (proximal, medial, distal) and an ontological one (entity, person, location, direction, manner, quality, quantity, etc.). The ontological (content) distinctions expressed by the demonstrative system of a language are typically also found in its subsystem of interrogatives (cf. Diessel 1999; Dixon 2003, Stolz – Levkovich – Urdze 2017). Grammatically, demonstratives can be characterized as closed-class items that form small contrastive sets, with distinctive properties of morphological combination and distribution in a clause (cf. Levinson 2018: 4).

The basic stages in the development of spatial demonstratives, adverbs and interrogatives in English are well-known (cf. Campbell 1991: 280; Mossé 1946; Stolz – Levkovich – Urdze 2017). In fact, the system of directional demonstratives in EME is frequently used as language of description for the analysis of related phenomena in other languages (Stolz – Levkovich – Urdze – Nintemann – Robbers 2017; Nintemann – Robbers – Hober 2020). The main novelty of our contribution consists in a more detailed and comprehensive analysis of the relevant changes with a focus on syntax and semantics, in combining qualitative methods with some quantitative observations and in assessing the results of the changes for a characterization of PDE from a comparative and typological perspective.

The structure of the paper is as follows: In the next four sections, the systems of spatial demonstratives, adverbs and interrogative pro-forms² are described

² Interrogative pro-forms are included, since they manifest morphemic and sub-morphemic similarities with demonstratives in English and, in fact, in a wide variety of languages, as well as analogous ontological differentiations and furthermore manifest similar historical developments: *whence* and *whither* are disappearing together with *hence* and *hither* (cf. Stolz – Levkovich – Urdze – Nintemann – Robbers, 2017).

for different historical periods of English, including their formal and semantic properties (spatial *vs.* extended use), their historical development and their loss. The results of this descriptive survey are then summarized and discussed from a more general, i.e. comparative and typological perspective. Our data are authentic examples taken from the relevant corpora of Old English, Middle English and Early Modern English (*Dictionary of Old English Corpus (DOEC)* online, Corpus of Middle English Prose and Verse (CMEPV), Early English Books Online (EEBO), English-Corpora.org – and dictionaries – *Dictionary of Old English (DOE)* A-I online, Bosworth-Toller, Middle English Dictionary Compendium (*MED*)). The examples from PDE are based on dictionaries, modern texts and information provided by native speakers, as well as on our own intuitions. Documentation for examples that are clearly instances of informal PDE, like (2)-(5) and (43)-(47) is not provided. Our method of analysis is primarily a qualitative rather than a quantitative one, but our results are also supported by the quantitative data collected for a limited time period and some easily accessible collections of data.

2. The system and use of spatial demonstratives in Old English

As a first step we will look at the systems of demonstratives, of spatial adverbs and of interrogatives in Old English (henceforth OE). The further development of these systems will be discussed in subsequent chapters. In Table 1 the subsystem of spatial demonstratives is embedded in the larger picture of available ontological dimensions. The table shows that right from the beginning of its documented historical development English only had a two-term system of deictic distinctions (proximal *vs.* distal)³, just like its Germanic relatives, but in contrast to the three-term systems of some Romance languages (e.g., Spanish), some Finno-Ugric languages (Finnish, Hungarian), some Slavic languages (Serbian, Bulgarian) and a wide variety of other languages with even richer systems. Moreover, in the ontological dimensions of MANNER (*swā, þus > so, thus*) and QUALITY (*swilc > such*) no deictic distinction is found (cf. Koenig – Vezzosi 2020), in contrast to Finnish, Serbian, Armenian and Japanese (*koo, soo, aa* ‘like this, like that’). It is also worthy of note that very similar demonstrative systems are found in Old Norse/Icelandic (cf. Table 2) and also Old High German.

³ The distinction between *hēr, þær* and *geond* (*here, there, yon(der)*) is, however, generally considered as an instance of a three-term deictic distinction analogous to Spanish *aquí* ‘here’, *ahí* ‘there’ and *allí* ‘over there’.

	ENTITY	TIME	PLACE	GOAL	SOURCE	MANNER	DEGREE	QUALITY
PROXIMAL	<i>þes</i>	<i>nū</i>	<i>hēr</i>	<i>hider</i>	<i>heonan</i>	<i>swā, þus</i>		<i>swilc</i>
DISTAL	<i>se</i>	<i>þā</i>	<i>þær geond</i>	<i>þider</i>	<i>þanon</i>			
INTERROG.	<i>hwæt</i>	<i>hwonne</i>	<i>hwær</i>	<i>hwider</i>	<i>hwanon</i>	<i>hū</i>		<i>hwilc</i>

Table 1. The system of demonstratives and interrogatives in Old English.

	ENTITY	TIME	PLACE	GOAL	SOURCE	MANNER	QUALITY
PROXIMAL	<i>þessi</i>	<i>nú</i>	<i>hér</i>	<i>hingað</i>	<i>héðan</i>	<i>svona</i>	<i>slíkur; svona</i>
DISTAL	<i>það</i>	<i>þa</i>	<i>þar</i>	<i>þangað</i>	<i>þaðan</i>		
INTERROG.	<i>hver; hvað</i>	<i>hvenær</i>	<i>hvar</i>	<i>hvert</i>	<i>hvaðan</i>	<i>hvernig</i>	<i>hvaða</i>

Table 2. The system of demonstratives and interrogatives in Icelandic⁴.

From the perspective of this study, the most interesting differentiations are the ones between the demonstratives expressing a location (PLACE) and two pairs of directional demonstratives referring to the target of DIRECTION, i.e., a SOURCE and to a GOAL of a motion event, respectively. The distinction between a proximal and a distal deictic expression for location seems to be a basic one in many languages, since the relevant demonstratives are frequently used to draw, strengthen or renew other deictic distinctions (cf. dialectal and colloquial Engl. *this* > *this here*, *that* > *that there*, Ger. *dies da* ‘this one’ – *das da* ‘that one’, Swed. *så här* ‘like this’ – *så där* ‘like that’, Fr. *voici* ‘here you are’ vs. *voilà* ‘there you are’). In the history of English this basic distinction between proximal “here” and distal “there” is attested in OE and in fact for all periods of the language:

PLACE

- (6) Her is his mildheortnes ofer us ac þær is se eca dom
 Here is his mercy upon us but there is the eternal judgement
 (HomU (Thorpe) 55 6).
 [In this world his mercy is upon us, but in that world is the eternal judgement]

Directional deixis, the focus of our study, is also clearly attested in OE. It is encoded by an opposition between two pairs of expressions referring either to the source or to the goal of a motion event, further distinguished in terms of “proximity to” vs. “distance from” a center of orientation: e.g., *heonan* ‘from here, hence’ vs. *þanon/þanan* ‘from there, thence’ and *hider* ‘to this place/place of the speaker,

⁴ Table 2 represents the deictic system of Modern Icelandic (Stefán Einarsson 1945), where the distinctions found in the older stages of Germanic languages (OE and OHG) have been retained.

hither⁵ vs. *þider* ‘to that place/a place contextually given, thither’. The following examples provide illustration:

SOURCE

- (7) *Ðis is eallunga min agen cyþ [...] ic wæs ær hionan cumen*
 this is entirely my own country I was before from. here come
 (Met. 24,49-51).
 [This is my very own country, I originally came from here.]

- (8) *þanon he com on Iudéisce endas*
 From. there he came to Judean border: ACC; PL (Mk (WSCp) 10.1).
 [From there he came to the borders of Judea]

GOAL

- (9) *þa cwæð se hælend hyre to: gang clypa þinne wer and cum hider þonne*
 Then said the Saviour her to: go embrace your man and come to. here then
 (ÆHom V, 33.699).
 [Then the Saviour said to her: go and embrace your husband and then come here.]

- (10) *Ða [...] ðe hine þider læddon*
 Those [...] who him to. there led (Or 5.2.116.9).
 [Then they led him there.]

In coordinate combinations, the directionals relating to the source and a goal of a motion event (*hider and þider*) lose their deictic meaning and simply express a multitude of directions, i.e., disorder in motion events:

- (11) *ða beseah he hine ymbutan hider & ðyder, & geseah þæt þær nan man*
 Then looked he him about here. to and there. to and saw that there no man
 gehende næs (Exod 2.12. cf. huc atque illuc).
 next NEG: was
 [Then he looked around him everywhere and saw that there was nobody.]

- (12) *hwæt, þa seo earma hind arn hider & þider mid miclan gedræfednesse*
 Look, then the poor hind ran here. to and there. to with great trouble: DAT
 (LS 9 (Giles) 250, cf. Vit. Aegid. 2.12 huc illucque diffugiens).
 [Look, the poor hind ran all over the place in great trouble.]

⁵ In combination with distal *geond*, *hider* many also assume a distal meaning ‘to a place over there’: Mt (WSCp) 26.36: *ða com se hælend mid him on þone tun ðe is genemned Gezemani & sæde hys leorningcnihtum: sittað her oðþæt ic ga hider geond & me gebidde*. [Then the Saviour came with him in the town that is called gethsemane and said to his disciples: sit here until I go to that place and I pray]. Note also that *yon*, the modern counterpart of *geond* in ModE may have a distal directional use: *hither and yon*.

This loss of the deictic component can be found in co-ordinations of all contrasting pairs of demonstratives encoding the same ontological dimension, in PDE and many other languages (*here and there, now and then, this and that, Italian *così o così* ‘like this or like that, etc.’*), and thus seems to be a very general feature in the use of such co-ordinations (cf. König 2020).

In addition to the systems of demonstratives described above, the older stages of Germanic languages also expressed spatial and directional distinctions by a system of inflecting, non-deictic adverbs. Since these formal distinctions between PLACE, SOURCE and GOAL are most clearly and consistently marked by inflectional forms in Old Norse and partly also in Modern Icelandic, we will first look at the relevant subsystem in Icelandic.

MEANING	DIRECTION: SOURCE	DIRECTION: GOAL	PLACE
‘in’	<i>innan</i> ‘from within’	<i>inn</i> ‘into’	<i>inni</i> ‘inside’
‘out’	<i>útan</i> ‘from outside’	<i>út</i> ‘out, towards the outer side’	<i>úti</i> ‘out’ (of place)
‘up’	<i>ofan</i> ‘from above’	<i>upp</i> ‘upward’	<i>uppi</i> ‘upon, above’
‘forward’	<i>framan</i> ‘forward, outward, from a place on the front side’	<i>fram</i> ‘toward the open’	<i>frammi</i> ‘in, on a place’
‘home’	<i>heiman</i> ‘from home’	<i>heim</i> ‘home(ward)’	<i>heima</i> ‘(at) home’

Table 2a. Spatio-directional adverbs and prepositions in (Old)Icelandic (Cleasby – Vigfusson 1874, Einarsson 1945: 60-63; Svenonius 2006).

The classification and glosses in the above diagram contain some simplifications, if the whole spectrum of uses given in Cleasby – Vigfusson (1874) is taken into account. Adverbs encoding the source of a motion event are apparently also used for PLACE in some cases. Such uses are, however, clearly marked as secondary by the authors.

In the analogous system of OE, the expression for SOURCE is still clearly distinguished in both form and meaning from the expressions for GOAL and PLACE, in contrast to the latter two, which are partly identical in form and overlapping in their meaning:

MEANING	DIRECTION: SOURCE	DIRECTION: GOAL	PLACE
‘in’	<i>innan</i> ‘from within’	<i>inn</i> ‘into’	<i>inne</i> ‘in, on, into’
‘out’	<i>ūtan</i> ‘from outside’	<i>ūt</i> ‘out’ (motion)	<i>ūte</i> ‘outside, abroad’
‘up’	<i>uppan</i> ‘from above, upon’	<i>upp</i> ‘above, upwards’	<i>uppe</i> ‘on high, up’
‘in front’	<i>foran</i>	<i>fore</i>	<i>fore</i>
‘far’	<i>feorran</i> ‘from afar’	<i>feorr</i> ‘far (away)’	<i>feorr</i> ‘distant’
‘south’	<i>suban</i> ‘from the south’	<i>sub</i> ‘southward’	<i>sub</i> ‘in the south’

Table 3. Spatio-directional adverbs in OE (Campbell 1991: 280).

A specification of direction is not only relevant for motion events (13), but also in transfer events (“caused motion” and “caused position”), as well as in perception events. In OE directional demonstratives are also found in expressions encoding those types of events: *hlyst hider* ‘listen to me’; *locode hider* ‘looked here’ (14).

- (13) þa cwæð ðe hælend [...]: ic com hider on dome on ðisne middaneard.
Then said the Saviour [...]: I come here. to in judgement in this:ACC world
(ÆHomM 2 102).
[Then said the Saviour: I have come to this world in order to administer justice.]
- (14) a. Þa ymbe lytel þa clypode se engel to Paule and cwæð him to: loca hider.
Then around little then called the angel to Paul and said him to: look here.to
(HomU 37 (Nap 46) 115).
[The a little later the angel addressed Paul and said to him: Look here!]
- b. [H]e cwæð: hlyst hider, ðu ðe eardasð on freondes orcegarde.
He said: listen here.to, you that live in friend:GEN orchard:DAT
(CP 49.381.12).
[He said: listen to me, you who live in the orchard of friends.]

Just like in the older stages of other Germanic languages and in Modern Icelandic, formal distinctions between PLACE *vs.* DIRECTION, on the one hand, and SOURCE *vs.* GOAL of a motion event were clearly established in OE, in a system of demonstratives, in a system of interrogatives as well as in a system of non-deictic spatial adverbs. The analysis of these systems of function words is our point of departure for a detailed discussion of the development, reduction and loss of these distinctions in the chapters following.

3. System and use in Middle English

At first sight the Middle English (henceforth ME) system of directional demonstratives and adverbs seems to have been almost identical to the OE one, insofar as the distinctions (between PLACE and DIRECTION and between SOURCE and GOAL of a motion event) made in OE (cf. Table 1) were largely maintained (Table 4)⁶. The basic use of the four directional demonstratives can be found in a single example:

- (15) Þe lord god lyueþ for his aungil kepte me, & hennys goyng & þere dwelling
The lord God lives for his angel kept me and here.from going and there dwelling

⁶ Differences between dialects and text types in this domain will only be considered in so far as they are significant for subsequent developments.

& þennys hider turnynge azee.
 and there.from here.to turning again (a1382 WBible(1) (Bod 959) Judith 13.20)⁷.
 [the Lord God lives, for his angel has kept me, both going from here, and dwelling there, and (re)turning again from there to this place.]

A closer look reveals, however, that the inventory of expressions encoding directions and paths of motion events was changing and had already changed significantly. First, non-deictic adverbial expressions of place lost the semantic opposition between PLACE and *goal*, i.e., *innan* and *inne*, though formally distinguished, were both used to identify a place ('inside, within'). Even more relevant for our study is the fact that the distinction between locative and directional demonstratives was formally reinforced, while the semantic distinction became blurred. Directional demonstratives extended their domains of usage, thus increasing their polysemy. As a consequence, there is overlap in meaning and ambiguity in usage.

PLACE	DIRECTION: GOAL	DIRECTION: SOURCE
<i>hēr</i>	<i>hider</i>	<i>henne, hennes⁸, hens(e)</i>
<i>Þær / geond</i>	<i>þider</i>	<i>thenne, thennes thens(e)</i>
<i>wher</i>	<i>whider</i>	<i>whenne</i>

Table 4. The system of spatial demonstratives and interrogatives in ME.

Locative demonstratives, i.e., *ther(e)* and *her(e)*, occasionally mark direction, thus foreshadowing a later development, simply expressing the distal (cf. (16a-b)) or proximal (cf. (17a-b)) location of the implied goal or source. Motion events from a source or to a goal tend to be expressed more and more by the *Aktionsart* (aspectual character) of the verb.

- (16) a. Folc þer com sone to þere burh of Rome.
 People there come soon to the:DAT city of Rome.
 (c1275 (?a1200) Lay. Brut (Clg A. 9)12651).
 [People came there soon, to the city of Rome] = DISTAL GOAL
- b. Þer sone after sche was ynome And yladde to hir dome.
 There soon after she was taken and lead to her judgement
 (c1330 Arth. & M. (Auch) 887).
 [From there, soon afterwards, she was taken and lead to her judgement] = DISTAL SOURCE

⁷ All quotations are taken from *CMEVP*, if not otherwise specified, and quoted according to the *MED*.

⁸ *Henne*, from the OE *heonan*, appeared in Middle English with adverbial genitive suffix *-es*, *-s*. From the early sixteenth century the final unvoiced *-s* began to be spelled as *-ce* as in *thence* etc.

- (17) a. He is iblescet þe þe her cumet on drihtenes nome.
 He is blessed REL REL here comes on Lord: GEN name
 (a1225 Lamb. Hom. (Lamb 487) 5).
 [Blessed is he who comes here in the Lord's name.] = PROXIMAL GOAL
- b. Siþþe hit was þat seint berin her bi weste wende
 After it was that Saint Berin here towards West turned (c1305 St. Swithin 9.43).
 [After it happened that Saint Berin went from here towards the West] = PROXIMAL SOURCE

What is also clearly attested in ME is the role of the predicate in the exact interpretation of directionals: DIRECTION is encoded with dynamic verbs, i.e. processes and events (18a), whereas stative verbs indicate DISTANCE in combination with directional demonstratives (18b).

- (18) a. Crist zeue us habbe swichne [McC: suicchne] ende þet we moten þider cumen
 Christ given us have end that we must there.to come
 þanne we hennes wende.
 when we here.from went (a1225 PMor. (Dgb 4)st. 191). = DIRECTION
 [Christ gave us such an end that we must come to that place when we leave from here.]
- b. Her woneþ, hennes [vr. hens] mani a mile, Mi broþer [...]
 Here lives, here. from many a mile, my brother
 (1330 (?c1300) Amis (Auch)953).
 [Here [Sir Amiloun] he lives, from here many miles, my brother.] = DISTANCE

Directional demonstratives in ME are not only found in constructions encoding motion towards a place, but may also be used for directing attention to an object in perception events. *Hider* began to be used in this sense as early as in OE (19a.-b.), but is now found in combination with all kinds of perception verbs. Moreover, *thens* begins to develop anaphoric and discourse functions, extending its possible point of reference from the speaker to the topic of the discourse, as in (20a.), where it expresses “motion away from a topic” and thus a change of discourse topic. A further instance of the metaphorical extension of motion events is the use of source markers for developments with causes or premises as point of orientation (20b.).

- (19) a. Hlesteð hider, hlesteð hider, ze modi menn.
 Listen here.to listen here.to you proud men
 (a1225(c1200) Vices & V. (1) (Stw 34)41/25).
 [Listen to me, listen to me, you proud men. (cf. Germ. *herhören*)]
- b. Hise eizene, þat hie ne bien to swiðe gawrinde hider and zeond
 His eyes, REL they not be too greatly look:PTCP:PRES here.to and beyond
 (a1225 Vices & V. (1) (Stw 34)133/26).
 [His eyes, that they not be too eagerly looking hither and beyond]

- (20) a. Now turne we thens and beholde hem the whiche stonden on the rightsyde.
 Now turn we there.from and consider them the who stood on the rightside
 (a1450 Aelred Inst. (2) (Bod 423)24/963).
 [Now we turn from that topic and consider those who stayed on the right side.]
- b. Of his wyn drunke þe jentilis & þennis þei ben to-sterid.
 Of his wine drank the heathens and there.from they are troubled
 (a1382) WBible(1) (Bod 959)Jer. 51.7).
 [The heathens have drunk from its wine, and thus they got confused.]

That *hens*, *thens* and *hider*, *thider* were undergoing a process of semantic bleaching during the ME period is further revealed by the adjunction of directional prepositions, such as *from* as a source marker (21a.-b.) and *till* or *to* as a goal marker (21c.-d.), whose additions reinforce the distinction between the source and the goal of a motion event.

- (21) a. Ther thou were wel, fro hennes artow weyued.
 There you were well, from here.from are.you waived
 (c1390 Chaucer CT. ML. (Manly-Rickert) B. 308).
 [Where thou were well, from there you are driven away]
- b. Þi gate Fro hennes to paradis ȝate.
 they got from here.from to paradise:GEN gate
 (a1325 Cursor Mundi (Trin. Cambr.) l. 1264).
 [They got from here to the heaven's gate]
- c. Swa many myle, Fra heven tulle hyder.
 So many miles from heaven to here. to
 (a1340 R. Rolle Pricke of Conscience 7746).
 [So many miles, from heaven to this place.]
- d. Be fflawme at had burnyd all þe town end to thedir sesid, & wold burn
 The flame forth had burned all the town and to there. to stopped and wanted
 burn no maner of þing of [hur] howse.
 no kind of thing of [their] house (c1450 Alph. Tales (Add 25719) 330/19).
 [the flame had burned down all the town and stopped there and wanted to burn nothing of their house.]

In addition to such reinforcement of directional markers, we also find their complete renewal through combinations of directional demonstratives with an adverbial suffix, such as *hiderward*, and *thiderward* (22), or, more significantly, of locative demonstratives with prepositions, such as *therto*, *therefrom* and *herto*, *herfro* (23):

- (22) a. Cnut [...] fundade hiderward & wolde gewinnan þis land mid
 Cnut went here.to.ward and wanted conquer this land with
 Rodbeardes eorles fultume of Flandran.
 Robert: GEN count: GEN help: DAT of Flanders (a1100 ChronE 1085 a. 1).
 [Cnut set out towards this place and wanted to conquer this land with the help of Robert count of Flanders.]

- b. Anon he wende þuderward wiþ vair compainie.
All. the. way he went from.there.onward with fair company
(a1297 R. Gloucester's Chron. (Rolls) 9183).
[He went all the way from there on with fair company]
- (23) a. Bus he hit gon dihten, and sparewen þerto liht.
Thus he it go dight and sparrows there.to alight
(c1275(?a1200) Lay. Brut (Clg A. 9) 14601).
[Thus he went to dispose of it and sparrows descended upon that place]
- b. Þis is nu þe forme dale þet haueð ispeken hiderto of ower seruise
This is now the previous part REL has uttered hither.to of your service
(?c1225 (?a1200) Ancrene Riwle (Cleo. C. vi) (1972) 38).
[The first part is now finished, which has spoken up to this point about your devo-
tional duties]
- c. Þreo milen þer-from to þan wuden þrunge nize þusende þe Arður
Three miles there-from to the wood thronged nine thousands REL Arthus
þider senden. Baldere Bruttus
there.to sent bald Brittons (c1275(?a1200) Lay. Brut (Clg A. 9)13277).
[Three miles from there to the wood thronged nine thousand bald Brittons that Ar-
thus had sent there]
- d. [...] is the occasioun wher-bi and wher-fro the goostli harme and
[...] [it] is the occasion where-near and where-from the spiritual harm and
synne comen⁹.
sin come
(c1449 Pecoock Repr. (Cmb Kk. 4.26)467).
[It is the occasion through which and from where the spiritual harm and sin come]

The creation of such “compounds” is an elaboration of a pattern already found in OE. Those including the proximal series (*herto*, *hertofore*, *hidertil*, *hiderto*, *hidertofore* etc.) had already developed a temporal and an anaphoric, discourse-functional use in OE – ‘up to now’, ‘up to this point’ – whereas in the distal series a basic directional meaning is still predominant in ME, the temporal use being marginal. Most compounds are preserved in Modern English and developed a temporal use in addition to their spatial one¹⁰, but are no longer found in modern usage, with the exception of highly formal or archaic style: e.g., *hereto*, *heretofore*, *hereafter*, *thereto*, *theretofore*, *therefrom*, *thereupon*, *whereupon*.

⁹ This example is added to show that spatial relatives derived from interrogatives show the same behaviour.

¹⁰ It is worth noting that in EModE the spatial use of those compounds does not disappear, but seems to be strengthened as their frequency of occurrence is even higher than in ME: *Hitherto shall ye come and no further* (1694 S. Johnson Notes Pastoral Let. 64), *Rede there and frothens forth into the eende of the argument* (c1449 R. Pecoock Repressor (1860) 540).

The extension of local concepts to temporal ones is a very wide-spread and possibly universal type of semantic extension (cf. Traugott 1978; Haspelmath 1997). In the history of English, such extensions are already found in OE texts, but are much more frequently attested in ME for the directional demonstratives relating to the source or the goal of a motion event. Analogously to its proximal directional use, *hider* is used to identify the end of a past time interval with the moment of utterance. Thus, in the following two examples both the beginning (SOURCE) and the end (GOAL) of a time interval are indicated:

- (24) a. From þat tyme hider the Sowdaun clepeth him self Calyffee.
From that time here.to the soldan called himself Caliph
(?a1425(c1400) Mandev. (1) (Tit C. 16)27/23).
[From that time up to now the sultan called himself Caliph.]
- b. We repute them as gentlemen descended lineally of worshipfull blood sithen the
We consider them as gentlemen descended lineally from honorable blood since the
Conquest hither.
conquest here. to (1466 Paston 4.246).
[We consider them gentlemen directly descended from noble blood since the Con-
quest.]

The source marker *hens*, by contrast, is either used retrospectively, i.e., to identify the beginning of an interval before the moment of utterance ('three days ago') or prospectively, for an interval after the moment of utterance ('three days hence'), depending on the tense of the sentence.

- (25) a. I bigan to sikynyn the thridde dai hens [WB(2): the thridde dai ago].
I began to sicken the third day here.from
(a1425(a1382) WBible(1) (Corp-O 4)1 Kings 30.13). = BACKWARDS FROM NOW
[I began to feel sick three days ago.]
- b. The thrydde day hens ye schul ben expirand.
The third day here.from you shall be die:PRS.PTCP
(?a1475 Ludus C. (Vsp D. 8)358/103). = FORWARD FROM NOW
[The third day from now you shall die.]

Only the forward-looking use of *hence* is still found in somewhat archaic and formal texts in Modern English:

- (26) I shall be telling this with a sigh
Somewhere ages and ages hence (Robert Frost, *The Road not Taken*)

It is particularly in the temporal domain that we find extensions in the use of locative and directional demonstratives in ME. This use for temporal intervals may also be reinforced by directional prepositions (*hitherto*, *hitherward*, *henceforth*, *henceforward*, *thenceforth*).

- (27) a. I, John Maundevylle [...] hiderto haue ben longe tyme ouer the see.
 I, John Mandeville, hitherto have been long time over the sea
 (?a1425(c1400) Mandev. (1) (Tit C. 16)3/21).
 [I, John Mandeville, was at sea a long time until that day.]
- b. Hennus forward, my britheren, haue 3e ioye in the Lord.
 Hence forward, my brethren, have you joy in the Lord
 (a1425(c1395) WBible(2) (Roy 1. C. 8)Phil. 3.1).
 [From now on, my brethren, rejoice in the Lord]
- c. For no wiht as by Ryht fro thennes forth þat hym lakketh goodnesse
 For no thing as by right from thence forth REL. him lacks goodness
 ne shal ben clepyd good.
 not shall be called good (c1374 G. Chaucer tr. Boethius De Consol. Philos. (Cambr.)
 iv. pr. iii. 86).
 [Because from now on no creature should be called good by right that lacks good-
 ness.]
- d. The Iewis weren charged with alle the lawis of resound with whiche the peple
 The Jews were charged with all the laws of reason with which the people
 fro Adam thidir to weren chargid
 from Adam there.to to were charged (c1449 R. Pecock Repressor (1860) 19).
 [The Jews were charged with all the laws of reason with which the people were
 charged from Adam up to now.]

It is also in ME that locative demonstratives (*here*, *there*) develop temporal uses on the basis of their spatial ones. Note that the relevant semantic change only affects the ontological (content) domain. The local demonstratives retain their proximal and distal meaning in relating to the more abstract content domain of time. *Hereto* and *heretofore* identify temporal intervals relative to the moment of utterance, just like *hitherto* ‘up to now’, whereas *thereupon*, *whereupon* and *theretofore* identify such intervals relative to a contextually given distant point in the past (‘immediately afterwards’ and ‘previously’).

The symmetrical system of spatial demonstratives manifested by OE, a system differentiated in terms of SOURCE, GOAL and PLACE in the content domain and in terms of PROXIMAL and DISTAL in the deictic domain, can still be found in ME, but a variety of changes indicate that this system is not stable any longer, neither in its formal nor in its semantic oppositions. The use of directional demonstratives is getting more and more reinforced by directional prepositions or is completely renewed by combinations of local demonstratives and spatial prepositions, both in the directional use and in a newly developing temporal use. A similar development can be observed in the system of spatial adverbs. This change can be assumed to be linked to a general restructuring process due to the loss of inflectional endings. The change affected all locative adverbials, where the relevant distinctions were already at jeopardy in OE. The forms ending in *-e* or *-i* merged with the suffixless forms due to the loss of unstressed final vowels, thus cancelling the formal distinction between goal and location, an information

easily retrieved by means of predicate meaning. The *-an* ending in local adverbials (e.g., *uti vs. utan*) was probably reinterpreted as an adjectival formative in analogy with the forms such as *wood vs. wooden*. Thus ME *outen* can be both an adverb and an adjective.

4. Early Modern English

The relevant cognate forms of the directional demonstratives are still found in Early Modern English (henceforth EModE) (*hither vs. thither* and *hence vs. thence*), just like the semantically analogous interrogative pronouns (*whither vs. whence*). Thus, the system of ME is largely preserved in its weakened formal and semantic oppositions, as shown in Table 5.

DEICTIC DIMENSION	DIRECTION: SOURCE	DIRECTION: GOAL	PLACE
PROXIMAL	<i>hence</i>	<i>hither</i>	<i>here</i>
DISTAL	<i>thence</i>	<i>thither</i>	<i>there</i>
INTERROGATIVE	<i>whence</i>	<i>whither</i>	<i>where</i>

Table 5: The system of spatial demonstratives in EME.

The tendencies observable in ME are further strengthened, however. *Hither* (also: *hitherward/s*, *hitherto*) and *thither* still express motion to a goal¹¹, but with a wide range of predicates it is not unusual to find locative demonstratives (*there* and *here*) for the goal of the motion event (28a vs. 28b and 29a vs. 29b). Source demonstrative, i.e., *hence* and *thence*, occur with the preposition *from* and without it with roughly equal frequency (*from hence/thence*). Evidence for this distribution can be found in the EEBO¹²: for the interval from 1500 to 1699, the frequencies of *from thence* and of *thence* are almost equal, adding up to 54% (55.684 tokens) and to 46% (47.663 tokens), respectively, whereas *from hence* (75%, that is 72913 tokens) occurs even more often than *hence* (25%, that is 23962 tokens). From the second half of the sixteenth century up to the end of the seventeenth century, *thence* and *hence* are rarely used by themselves to refer to the source of a motion event, but are reinforced in that function by the preposition *from* (*from hence*, *from thence*). At the same time, a complete renewal of “ablative” directionals can be observed: *hence* and *thence* are replaced by combinations of the preposition

¹¹ Cf. *I am heartily glad I came hither to you.* (As You Like it I.i.148), *This wrastler shall cleare all: nothing remaines, but that I kindle the boy thither* (As You Like it I.i.162).

¹² We are aware that EEBO is not a balanced linguistic corpus in terms of genre and that our figures are not statistically significant. What we want to show is a general trend.

from and the locative demonstratives *here* and *there* (*from here, from there*). This emerging pattern is, however, still rare, if compared to the reinforcement of the original source markers *thence/hence* with the “ablative” preposition *from* (cf. 30 a.-b.): in the *EEBO from there* (cf. 30 c.) and *from here* (30 d.) occur in only 20 and 11 instances respectively, but in both spatial and temporal reference (30 e.).

- (28) a. Vnder the greene wood tree, who loues to lye with mee. Come hither [...] (a1616 Sh. As you like It ii.v.5).
 b. Returne him here againe (1616 Sh. Measure for Measure v.i.376).
- (29) a. Farewell; go, say I sent thee thither (1616 Sh. Measure for Measure iii. ii. 35).
 b. And will not let a false sound enter there (1593 Sh. Venus & Adonis sig. F).
- (30) a. He commanded Victor [...], to come from thence unto him. (1609 Holland, tr. Amm. Marc. Rom. Hist. xxi.x.177).
 b. Richard not farre from hence hath hid his head (1597 W. Shakespeare Richard II iii. iii. 6).
 c. [...] not past three myles distaunce from there (Holinshed, Raphael 1577, from EEBO).
 d. [they] made intercession for him to the king, for his return into england, from here (Prynne, William 1665, p: 392 from EEBO).
 e. being now more then xv monythes from here (1558, The lame[n]tacion of England, from EEBO).

Note that the reinforcement of the demonstratives indicating SOURCE, i.e., *hence* and *thence*, by the “ablative” preposition *from* (*from hence/thence*) has no parallel in the further development of the goal-demonstratives.

The directional demonstratives in EModE also retain the temporal use found in ME, both for the goal (*hitherto*) and source expressions (*hence, henceforth, henceforward*). In both cases they are also frequently accompanied by a tense marker, a preposition or adverb with a basically directional meaning, indicating compositionally the direction of the relevant intervals from a starting point in the past to the moment of utterance (*hitherto*) or from the moment of utterance into the future (*forward, forth*).

- (31) We have been guided by thee hitherto (1616 Sh. Henry VI III. iii. 9).
- (32) Ile meet you at that place some houre hence (1616 Sh. Comedy of Errors iii.i.123).

What is rarely found, however, in contrast to ME, is the use of *hence* (*hennes*) relating to a period in the past looking backward from the moment of utterance (25). On the other hand, EModE directional demonstratives increase in the range of their possible contexts, in polysemy and polyfunctionality, indicating motion from various kinds of sources and to various types of goals:

- (33) a. And thys is also a deuice fit ynough for such a soli|citer, as is that false Scot prelate Rosse, mortall enemy hether [to him], vvho is presently in Fraunce (1579 Stubbs, Discouerie Gaping Gulf. EEBO).
- b. This wrastler shall cleare all: nothing remaines, but that I kindle the boy thither [for that purpose] (a1616 Sh. As you like It i.i. 162).
- c. [...] from hence [from this premise] that diuine philosopher draweth this conclusion, that the life of a wise man ought to be a perpetual meditation of death [etc.]. (1586 La Primaudaye & Bowes, The French academie wherin is discoursed the institution of maners, EEBO).
- d. Weigh every Circumstance, each Consequence, And usual Accident arising thence [consequently] (1692 Walker tr. Epictetus Enchiridion ix).

The ME system of spatial demonstratives and analogous interrogatives in its somewhat blurred semantic distinctions is still found in EModE. The tendencies of changing these systems observed in ME continue to manifest themselves even more clearly, however. The complete loss of all morphological distinctions, including the genitive case in adverbial (temporal and local) functions, deprive directional demonstratives of their paradigmatic relations. Consequently, the ME system of spatial demonstratives and analogous interrogatives in its somewhat blurred semantic distinctions is still found in EModE. The tendencies of changing these systems observed in ME continue to manifest themselves even more clearly, however.

5. Late modern English: descriptions and actual usage

Late Modern English (henceforth LModE) has traditionally been described as the age of prescriptivism and codification, given the emergence of all kinds of codifying manuals offering a normative view of the language. The descriptions and prescriptions of the usage of directional demonstratives, given in grammars and dictionaries from the first Latin-English grammars of the seventeenth century to the grammars and dictionaries of the eighteenth century, are based on the model of Latin and reinstate implicitly the system of OE. In Latin-English grammars (among many others, see Wallis 1653 and Cooper 1685) the dependence on the Latin model is even more evident, since the system of LModE directional demonstratives are analysed as totally parallel to its Latin counterpart:

DIRECTION: SOURCE	DIRECTION: GOAL	PLACE
<i>hence – hinc</i>	<i>hither – huc</i>	<i>here – hic</i>
<i>thence – illinc</i>	<i>thither – illuc</i>	<i>there – ibi</i>

Table 6. English directional demonstratives opposed to their Latin counterparts in LModE grammars.

What is clearly revealed by these grammars and language manuals are apparent changes in the system of encoding direction and attempts to correct current usage in terms of formulations that were not in line with the recommendations given. For instance, in his treatise on a *New National Grammar* (1706) Johnson uses *thence* and *hence* together with what he considered as a pleonastic preposition – a constructions despised as «a barbarous expression» or as «a vitious expression» by Samuel Johnson in his *Dictionary* (1755) – but only as anaphoric discourse-functional element (34).

- (34) The true reason of Disproportionate Comparison is nothing else but the Arbitrary Will of Mankind, which at pleasure overrules the ordinary Rules. From hence it has happen'd, that [...] (1706: 233)

A revealing statement of current usage in the 19th century together with strong criticism and recommendations is found in the following quotation:

The adverbs *hence*, *thence*, and *whence* imply a preposition; for they signify “from this place, from that place, from what place”. It seems, therefore, to be improper to join a preposition along with them, because it is superfluous: yet the practice is very common. [...]. “An ancient author prophecies from hence”. But the origin of these words is little attended to, and the preposition *from* is so often used in construction with them, that the omission of it, in many cases, would seem stiff and disagreeable. [...] The adverbs *here*, *there*, *where* are often improperly applied to verbs signifying motion, instead of the adverbs *hither*, *thither*, *whither*.: as, “He came here hastily.” They should be, “He came hither” (Murray 1823: 171)

The incongruity of these recommendations with the actual practice of the author is evident in the following example:

- (35) If, I say, omitting these things, we compare the causes themselves, in which each side is engaged, we may learn from thence how despicable they are (Murray 1816: 516)

5.1. Quantitative support from Late Modern English texts

So far, our methodology has exclusively been a qualitative one. The availability of large corpora of data enables us, however, to underpin our observations by quantitative data. In Jawzal – Omar (2020) the decline in the frequency of directional demonstratives and interrogatives is presented from the beginning of the nineteenth century to the end of the twentieth century in steps of 2 decades on the basis of the *COHA* (Corpus of historical American English). The figures differ somewhat from instance to instance, but the general tendency emerging is very clear: The frequency percentage of the relevant lexical items decreases

dramatically, though not always steadily, from the beginning of the nineteenth century to the end of the twentieth century. Frequencies fluctuate in some cases, but the frequency of all the relevant expressions have declined by 90% at the end of the last century.

In order to enrich this general view with more specific information on the eighteenth century, as well as on the reinforcement (*hence* > *from hence*) and renovation of directional deictics (*from hence/thence* > *from here/there*), we investigated the occurrence of the four directional demonstratives in prepositional phrases in English. corpora. org, in particular the British Google Books n-gram corpus for the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, (1700-1890), analyzing frequencies and contexts of usage. We are aware of the limited scope of the text collection in Google Books n-gram. It is, however, the large size of the corpus that allows us to have a clear, macro-perspective of the use of the individual items. The calculations have been made in absolute terms, that is, counting the occurrences of the original demonstratives (*hence*, *thence*, *hither*, *thither*) and comparing them to the figures found for their expansions in prepositional phrases (*from thence* and *from there*, *to/till thither* and *to/till there*), with and without concomitant replacement of the directional demonstrative by the locative one. In order to distinguish the main functions of these expressions we have also looked at their collocations with verbal predicates whose meaning might favor either the directional or the discourse-functional interpretations.

Figure 1. Frequency of source demonstratives: simple vs. complex patterns in LModE.

The first results show a surprising picture where the three patterns under comparison appear to manifest a differential behavior: In the case of source demonstrative constructions (Figure 1), the combination *from* + *thence* turns out to be predominant up to the first decade of the nineteenth century, after which the use of unexpanded *thence* increases. Only in the last decades of the nineteenth century

does the pattern P+*there* emerge. This last period witnesses the rise of P+*here* as well, which exceeds P+*hence* in frequency, the simple form being by far predominant in absolute terms, however.

A more detailed look reveals, however, that these figures are by no means incompatible with the qualitative observations made above. Introduced as a source marker for the reinforcement of *hence* and *thence*, the ablative preposition *from* disappears again before its reappearance in combination with the simple local demonstratives (*from here, from there*). This latter development did not occur before the end of the nineteenth century. The difference in the rate of decline of *from thence* as opposed to *from hence* could well be a consequence of the much more frequent use of *hence* in anaphoric, argumentative contexts.

While the simple forms seem to be used continuously during the whole period, it is the competing prepositional pattern (P+*thence/hence*) that shows a significant decline. Looking at their collocations we can observe that the contexts of occurrence appeared to be quite distinct from the ones found for *hither* and *thither* in that *thence* and *hence* appear to occur preferably either in passive constructions and impersonal constructions or with active verbs that do not exclusively encode motion events. *Thence*, in particular, is highly frequent in passive construction with predicates such as *derived, calculated, given, found* and so on, followed by motion verbs such as *removed, brought, driven, sailed, taken, carried*; alternatively, it occurs with active predicates either of concrete motion (e.g. *to depart* and *come*) or with more abstract ones (such as *to proceed, conclude, derive, know, follow, return, arise, infer, ensue*). Similarly, *hence* has two main patterns of occurrence, i.e., (i) passive constructions such as *it is/was hence that* and *it is/was* + Adjectives (e.g., *evident, manifest, demonstrable*) or Past Participles (e.g., *inferred, known* and the like), or (ii) in active constructions, such as *to have reason to, it happens/follows* etc., and with mental predicates such as *conclude, take, know, follow, infer*, and so on. In other words, *thence* and *hence* tend to be used in non-spatial contexts, whereas their prepositional expansions are primarily found in combination with predicates encoding motion events (in the order of collocation preference, *to go, walk, move, get, start, leave, send, run, lead, escape, depart, remove, sail, drive*, and so on).

Prototypical verbs of motion, i.e., *go* and *come* provide clear evidence for this tendency; with *come* and *go*, the prepositional phrases are the preferred option, whereas the simple demonstratives decline steadily in such contexts from the half of the eighteenth century onwards.

As far as the goal demonstratives are concerned, the simple forms *hither* and *thither* unexpectedly prevail during the whole period, with a strong decline starting in the second half of the eighteenth century, the complex forms being always very marginal. This, however, is simply a manifestation of the asymmetrical development of source and goal markers, which ultimately leads to the loss of the distinction between GOAL and PLACE. The replacement of *hither* and *thither* by

here and *there* in the expression of the goal of the motion event is again a late development, not clearly visible in the nineteenth century. That the use of simple *hither* and *thither* prevails longer than the analogous one of their counterparts for source is a clear manifestation of their asymmetric development and its results.

Figure 2. Frequency of simple and complex source demonstratives in collocation with motion verbs.

Figure 3. Frequency of goal demonstratives: simple vs. complex patterns in LModE.

6. Contemporary English: Further loss and renewal of distinctions

Compared to the changes observable in the preceding periods, the step from EModE and LModE to PDE is a more dramatic one and an instance of an “apparent” change, i.e. of a change still in progress today. In addition to Icelandic, English is the only modern West Germanic language that has preserved the inventory of formal distinctions in the domain of spatial demonstratives and interrogatives

found in earlier periods of its history, albeit in different phonological forms, uses and contexts. The relevant forms can still be found in formal, literary and archaic style, but some of the directional distinctions (source *vs.* goal) and some of the deictic distinctions (proximal *vs.* distal) of earlier periods are no longer attested. More important in present usage are some of the non-basic temporal and anaphoric, discourse-functional uses of the relevant forms. The current usage of the directional demonstratives inherited from EModE can be described as follows:

Hence has preserved its ablative (“from a source”) and partly also its deictic meaning, but the spatial use is no longer the most important one. Listed in the order of their historical development, the source can be a spatial one (archaic), a temporal one (“moment of utterance”) or a premise in an argument. The spatial use, the presumed origin of the other uses, is archaic, however, and only rarely mentioned in dictionaries. Given that the sequence of meanings or uses given in dictionaries for the lexical entries generally expresses a ranking in the frequency of current usage, the following ranking represents the frequency of current usage: (a) an anaphoric discourse-functional and argumentative use, (b) a temporal use (“period after the moment of orientation”), (c) a spatial use (“away from this place”).

(36) Peter is leaving at the end of this week – hence his anxiety to get his work finished.

(37) The project should be completed by next March, two months hence.

(38) Henceforward Britain and France had a common interest.

(39) Get you hence! (*Cambridge English Dictionary*)

The complex forms *henceforth* and *henceforward* only have a temporal use and differ from *hence* in identifying the duration of a situation from a point of orientation onwards, rather than the distance between two points-in-time.

Thence is still used anaphorically both in its original spatial sense and in the derived temporal one (*thenceforth*) as the distal counterpart of *hence*. The “source of a motion event” may also correspond to the starting point of a change. According to the entries in the major dictionaries, such as the *OED* online, the original spatial use is still the major one, although only in literary style, with the discourse anaphoric use in second position.

(40) We went to Mestre and thence to Venice by boat.

(41) The conversion of sunlight into heat and thence to electricity.

(42) The property was known thenceforth as The Manor. (all from the *Cambridge English Corpus*)

Hither has clearly preserved the (proximal) deictic and the allative (goal-directed) aspects of its meaning, but it is often characterized as “obsolete”. The non-deictic use in combination with *thither* seems to be the most frequent one. Only the complex form *hitherto* is used in a temporal sense.

- (43) Let the notes be sent to me hither.
 (44) They ran hither and thither.
 (45) This phenomenon was hitherto unknown.

Thither is only used as the anaphoric (DISTAL) counterpart of *hither*, as well as in the coordinate expression mentioned in (44).

- (46) They have dragged themselves thither for shelter. (Collins-Cobuild Advanced Dictionary, s.v. *thither*)

The parallel system of locative and directional distinctions still found in EModE is being partly renewed in dialects with the help of a basic demonstrative and a grammaticalized noun in American dialects: *this-a-way* vs. *that-a-way*. The grammaticalization of the noun *way* as a source marker in the standard varieties (*John moved away from London. Go away!*) is another manifestation of such renewals.

- (47) Let us go this-a-way rather than that-a-way (song by Ella Jenkins)

7. Summary and Conclusion

Starting out from the observation that Modern English has largely lost its formal means for distinguishing location from direction – like Italian and French, but unlike Icelandic and German – this article aims to show that, in addition to the loss of an adverbial system of inflectional distinctions in ME, a reorganization of the demonstrative system has played a major role in this process of loss. If certain details are neglected, the development of directional demonstratives can be summarized as follows:

- (48) Line of development
 heonan > henne(s) > hence > from hence > from here (SOURCE, PROXIMAL)
 þanon > thenne(s) > thence > from thence > from there (SOURCE, DISTAL)
 hider > hither > (to hither) > to here > here (GOAL, PROXIMAL)
 þider > thither > (to thither) > to here > here (GOAL, DISTAL)

Up to EModE and LModE, both locative and directional demonstratives were part of the relevant system, the latter furthermore differentiating between expressions for source and for goal. Vestiges of the system handed down to EModE from earlier periods (*hence – thence, hither – thither*) are still found in formal and archaic texts in PDE, but no longer play a role in colloquial and conversational English. Moreover, as pointed out above, these traces of an earlier spatial system have largely lost their original directional and deictic uses and are only rarely renewed in regional varieties of the language. The ordering of surviving uses according to frequency provided by major dictionaries shows that it is mainly the later developed non-spatial uses that have survived.

Another important aspect of the changes described above is the differential development manifested by source markers as opposed to goal markers, thus providing further evidence for the observation of a pervasive asymmetry between the marking of these directional concepts with other formal means made in a variety of recent cross-linguistic studies (Ikegami 1987; Stefanowitsch – Rohde 2004; Luraghi – Nikitina – Zanchi 2017; Stolz – Lestrade – Stolz 2014; Stolz – Levkovych – Urdze – Nintemann – Robbers 2017; Stolz – Levkovych – Urdze 2017; Verkerk, 2017; Stefanowsitsch 2018; Kopecka – Vuillermet 2021). The marginal use of *hence* as a proximal deictic marker for the source of a motion event, in contrast to the still possible use of *hither* and *thither* in their original directional (GOAL) and deictic sense is one manifestation of this asymmetry. Much stronger evidence can be seen in the general formal marking of SOURCE by the preposition *from* as opposed to the loss of the distinction between GOAL vs. PLACE and the resultant lack of formal marking for GOAL in English. Note furthermore that only source markers develop a discourse functional (argumentative) use.

The relevant semantic distinction between PLACE and DIRECTION are today almost exclusively carried by the preposition *to* and by adjectives or adverbs with the derivational morpheme *-ward(s)* (*toward, westward, homeward, upward, onward, leftward, wayward, etc.*), the latter expressing direction without implying a goal. In most other cases the distinction between location vs. direction is expressed by stative vs. dynamic verbs, as in (3)-(5) and in the following examples:

- (49) a. John went home an hour ago.
b. I went to see John, but he was not home.
- (50) a. John flew from New York to Toronto.
b. John is from Toronto.
- (51) a. Research and jobs in this area would simply go elsewhere.
b. If the car is not here it must be elsewhere.
- (52) a. We went across the road.
b. John lives across the road.

- (53) a. We went inside that haunted house.
 b. They lived inside a castle.

Let us now reconsider our observations on the development of directional demonstratives and adverbs from broader comparative, typological and explanatory perspectives, in relation to questions like the following: In what way are the relevant changes instances of general developments observable across languages? How can we explain the relevant changes? In what way do their results contribute to a reorganization in the structures of English?

Are the developments described above clear instances of grammaticalization? This question cannot be answered in the affirmative. Demonstratives are at the origin of a wide variety of grammatical markers (*cf.* Diessel 1999; 2006) and are even considered as sources of all grammatical markers in Brugmann (1904). However, a characterization of the relevant development as processes of change through which grammatical markers become more grammatical does not seem to be convincing either, given that the changes manifested by the directional demonstratives in English essentially involve semantic change, loss of semantic oppositions and substance, rather than concomitant changes on various parameters. What is maintained in archaic and formal English are primarily the metaphorical extensions from the spatial into the temporal and discourse-functional domains. These results are very different from the ones attested in the other West-Germanic languages, in particular from the relevant changes in German, where two goal markers (*hin, her*) from the original four-term system have developed into deictic clitics and combine with a variety of lexical categories.

For the goal bias in the encoding of motion events, some general explanations have been formulated in terms of non-linguistic factors, such as the cognitive and pragmatic salience of the goals, rather than the beginnings, of human actions and the higher information value of goal markers in conceptualizing a motion event in its entirety (*cf.* Lakusta – Landau 2005; Stefanowitsch 2018; Kopecka – Vuillemet 2001 for recent overviews). The only part that is missing in these explanations is an answer to the question how the different manifestations of an asymmetry in form and frequency are related to each other. Haspelmath's views on the tie-up between frequency, predictability and shortness of coding seem to provide this missing link (*cf.* Haspelmath 2021). That the goal of a motion event is much more frequently encoded than its source has been pointed out for a wide variety of languages. On the basis of a rich collection of cases and data from various domains of grammar, Haspelmath has argued that there is a causal connection between an asymmetry in the frequency of encoding a category and the brevity of its encoding in contrast to a minimally different category of the same "paradigm". Frequency of encoding results in a high degree of predictability of the relevant information, so that only minimal or zero marking is required for efficient communication.

The following assumption about relevant causal chains thus has a high degree of plausibility:

(54) frequency predictability shortness of encoding.

What ultimately underlies all three factors can then be seen in the cognitive and pragmatic factors mentioned above.

Considered from a typological perspective, the loss of a formal distinction between the encoding of GOAL and of PLACE can be analyzed as another instance of a loss of distinctions preserved in the systems of other Germanic languages and, more specifically, of the boundary permeability, i.e., of a fluid transition between two categories, identified by Berg (2014) for English. Just as the distinctions between different parts of speech (*be blind, to blind, the blind*), between countable and uncountable nouns (*two tables, enough table for everybody*) and between verbs and nouns (*to run, a run*) is less strictly drawn in English than in German and thus more “permeable”, in Berg’s terminology, the distinction between location and direction is a “soft boundary” in English in contrast to German and Icelandic.

Abbreviations

ACC	Accusative
DAT	Dative
DOE	Dictionary of Old English
EEBO	Early English Books Online
EModE	Early Modern English
GEN	Genitive
IMP	Imperative
LModE	Late Modern English
MED	Middle English Dictionary
ME	Middle English
NEG	Negation
OE	Old English
PTCP	Participle
PL	Plural
PRES	Present
PDE	Present-Day English
REL	Relative marker

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